

PEDAGOGICAL VALUE OF RECYCLING LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *Language processing is when learners practice language they have learned before. Recycled language is reintroduced in a different context or through a different skill. It helps the student to expand the scope of using something new. Recycling is an important part of the consolidation of learning. It is often included in course and course book structures. Teachers can look for opportunities to recycle new language through varying the skills work a class meets.*

Key words: *recycling, specific task, consolidation of learning, recycling lexical elements, interchanged, long-term.*

ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЕ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ЯЗЫКА ПЕРЕРАБОТКИ

Аннотация. *Языковая обработка — это когда учащиеся практикуют язык, который они выучили ранее. Переработанный язык повторно вводится в другом контексте или с помощью другого навыка. Это помогает учащемуся расширить сферу использования чего-то нового. Повторное использование является важной частью консолидации обучения. Он часто включается в структуру курсов и учебников. Учителя могут искать возможности перерабатывать новый язык, варьируя навыки, с которыми сталкивается класс.*

Ключевые слова: *рециклинг, конкретная задача, закрепление заучивания, рециклинг лексических элементов, взаимозаменяемость, долговременность.*

INTRODUCTION

Recycling is the practice of previously observed language by students. The recycled phrase will be reintroduced in a new setting or using a new technique. This enables the pupil to utilize the new object more diversely. The consolidation of learning involves a lot of recycling. Structures for courses and course books frequently feature it. By altering the skill work a class completes, teachers can seek for opportunities to recycle new language. Our belief is that utilizing the same language in a variety of tasks is the greatest method to incorporate possibilities for recycling inside courses. This is simple when using the PPP paradigm (Presentation - Practice - Production), since you give instances of new language by reading or listening, practice it through carefully graded oral and written activities, and then reuse it in free writing, maybe as a homework assignment. In a following class, we may revisit the same language and perhaps add a little more, either by utilizing the same exercises again or by creating new ones. The assignments listed below can be used to introduce and practice the past tense in a single session or a series of lessons. Each task could just take a short while. Even when the specific task varies, we will see how the same language is repeated.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Every repetition increases the likelihood that the pupils' brains will create long-term memories of the sounds, language, and structures that can serve as the foundation for independent usage in the future. There will be plenty of opportunities to recycle language, especially high frequency language, in a well-planned course. A vocabulary or grammar topic will be reviewed at least once a year and maybe more frequently under the so-called spiral

curriculum approach found in many textbooks. One critique of this methodology is that because there is such a lengthy time between each "revisit," many students have forgotten what they previously learned, necessitating a new round of instruction. This is a frequent grumble among language instructors. The approach is to make sure that each week you make an effort to use crucial vocabulary as frequently as you can in fresh situations and to recycle it in classroom conversation. For example, you may ask L2 students what they did over the weekend to review the preterit/perfect tense. Students are more likely to forget what they have done if we do not do this and simply go on to a new topic, entirely ignoring the prior one. If we had our own classroom, we could guarantee that knowledge is maintained by keeping the most important parts of each lesson on a "teaching wall."

The idea of recycling lexical elements comes from the Lexical Approach to English Language Teaching (ELT). It is regarded as a change from the conventional paradigm, in which language training moves from grammar to vocabulary/lexis. This article's primary goal is to emphasize the value of recycling for ELT and English Language Learning (ELL). It gives a succinct overview of the state of the English language today. A brief history of ELT teaching methodologies and approaches is also reviewed, which led to the paradigm change from grammar- to lexis-centered language education. A thorough discussion of the lexical approach is given, with specific attention paid to the value of reusing lexical terms throughout the language-learning process. The researcher held focus group talks against this backdrop to offer time-tested strategies to realistically use the idea of recycling in vocabulary instruction successfully. Research findings are presented using the information gathered during focus group talks.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Recycling is practicing language that learners have seen previously. The recycled language will be re-introduced in a different context, or through a different skill. This helps the student extend their range of use of the new item.

The words "recycling" and "repetition" are frequently interchanged. Traditional approaches, in which linguistic chunks must be repeatedly practiced until they become second nature, have been characterized by the latter. Mechanical, or rote, learning is a style of learning that is characterized by repetition. However, as a result of unhappiness with traditional behaviorist approaches, the mechanical features of the process were rethought; it was distinguished from recycling in that the latter entails meaningful recurrence. Recycle is to rejuvenate, re-teach, and relearn something. In other words, " Recycling should not be confused with 'repetition,' and it should thus be envisioned as a snowball' that allows the vocabulary seen previously a 'second chance' to be corrected, expanded, and enhanced". Repetition is consciously and continuously repeated, emphasizes on memorization through oral practices, inability to produce or generate language. Recycling is meaningful repetition, addressing learners' needs of language exposure, restructuring language, cognitive development.

To begin, it's important to note that vocabulary recycling is, in some ways, a practical manner of revisiting previously learned terminology. There are, however, a number of practical tasks in which recycling might be more visibly manifested. The nature of vocabulary knowledge, namely receptive and productive information, can be used to split vocabulary-recycling activities.

There are a number of practical tasks that can be used to recycle useful vocabulary knowledge. When dealing with new issues, one of these actions is brainstorming past phrases

and similar words. This practice assists learners in activating their internal lexical syllabi. Furthermore, writing book reviews might aid with vocabulary recycling because students will seek to replicate terminology learnt before in the writing activity. Finally, testing might be viewed as a means of encouraging pupils to reread language. In fact, language attrition is particularly vulnerable to the productive component of vocabulary knowledge. "Learners' production competence in the lexicon was initially forgotten while their receptive skill was immune," Tomiyama claimed in this regard. As a result, there should be more activities that emphasize the usefulness of vocabulary knowledge.

DISCUSSION

Finally, numerous approaches to using recycling to prevent vocabulary attrition have been taken. Recycling originated as a practical technique to retain lexical competence in second and foreign languages as a result of the insufficiency of repetition in preventing attrition of an acquired foreign language. Recycling is important because it helps to eliminate the key causes of language attrition by employing a variety of approaches that try to reactivate receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge.

Students will benefit greatly from the chance to learn new vocabulary in English lessons on a range of subjects. In order for pupils to "own" these terms and begin to use them with assurance, English teachers should urge their students to review this vocabulary on a regular basis.

Chatting: It is definitely worth chatting to pupils and finding out how and where they keep track of new terms that are mentioned in class if they believe that enough effort isn't being put into learning new vocabulary. They could not have a system in place or they might have a notepad where they record the new terms. Encouragement should be given to all pupils to try their best to organize their vocabulary recording. You may bring in your notebook and demonstrate how you are trying to expand your own vocabulary if you are learning a new language and somehow keeping track of new words.

"Word bag" envelope: Another approach to have quick access to the terms that have come up in your lessons, aside from urging your students to keep a tidy vocabulary book of some form, is to make a "word bag" for each of your groups. Two sizable envelopes and some card strip are all that are required. Write "Blank word cards" on one envelope and "Class word bag" on the other. Put several little card strips that have been cut into strips in the envelope labeled "Blank word cards." Choose a student from each class to manage the "word bag." He or she is in charge of writing all the new vocabulary on unique blank word cards and placing them in the class word bag envelope after receiving the envelopes at the start of the lesson. If your group can't do this, you can be in charge of putting the words in the bag after each lesson. It would be simpler for you to keep track of the bag if you can keep the envelopes in the class where you teach, fastened on a notice board or in a secure location. You'll have a solid assortment of words in the word bag after a few classes. Here are some exercises for recycling vocabulary while utilizing the word bag. They can be used as a warm-up at the start of a class or in the final five minutes.

Quick fire quiz: Pull out a bunch of words from the bag. Give clues or definitions so the students can guess the word on the card. The student who guesses the word correctly wins the card. The winner is the student with the most cards at the end.

Beep' sentences: Read a sentence incorporating the word on the word card. Instead of saying the word, say 'beep'. Students guess the missing word. When students get the idea, pass them the word bag, so they can create their own sentences.

Circle story: Give each student a word card. You start and begin to tell a story and use the word you have on your card. When you have used your word, the next student continues the story until they can incorporate their own word.

Team vocab tests: Divide the class into teams or pairs. Pull out a set number of words and using translation or clues give the teams a vocab test!

Pictionary: In two teams, use the word cards as prompts for a game of Pictionary. Use the board or paper. The word bag will have many applications as you use it more. Students, in my experience, feel more secure knowing what vocabulary will be tested, and they can feel quite proud of themselves when they feel comfortable using new terms. For many pupils, learning vocabulary requires a lot more work than we and they would like to admit. The word bag alleviates the perception that learning new English words is a "bottomless pit"! It could make learning more realistic and attainable.

CONCLUSION

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